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1 M2.6 Initial FAIR implementation workshops

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Dissemination Level

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2 Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Author	Notes
0.1	31.08.2023	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	TOC and V0.1
0.2	31.08.2023	Vasso Kalaitzi and Lisa de Leeuw (DANS)	review of v0.1
1.0	31.08.2023	Joy Davidson (DCC-UEDIN)	updated version for publication

Disclaimer

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

4 Introduction

Our FAIR Implementation Workshop series help three key stakeholders - Research performing Organisations, Repositories & Data Service Providers, and National Level Initiatives - to become familiar with FAIR-enabling tools, approaches and methods. Each workshop will provide an overview of a specific FAIR-enabling activity, share information on recent developments both from within FAIR-IMPACT and other initiatives as well as offering examples of good practice, practical tips and recommendations. Each workshop will last a maximum in 90 minutes and include plenty of time for questions and discussion. Registration is free and open to all. This report provides an overview of the first five FAIR Implementation Workshops that have been delivered by the FAIR-IMPACT project during the first year of the project.

5 Description of the Milestone

This brief milestone report provides an overview of the first five FAIR Implementation Workshops that have been delivered by the FAIR-IMPACT project.

5.1 Role of the milestone

This report is intended to provide information about the workshops delivered during the first year of the FAIR-IMPACT project. The workshops have been focussed around the open calls for support.

5.1.1 Means of verification

The table below includes a summary of the five FAIR Implementation workshops that were held during the first year of the project.

Table 1. FAIR Implementation workshops

Workshop	Date	Registrants	Materials
	Monday 27 March 2023 15:00 – 16:00 CEST	126	Slides and recording are available from the website: https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/webinar-fair-impact-open-call-support
	Tuesday 16 May 2023 15:00 – 16:00 CEST	37	Slides and recording are available from the website: https://fair-impact.eu/events/fairimpact-events/webinar-fair-impacts-virtual-clinic-potential-applicants-first-open-call

	Friday 25 August 2023 10:00 – 11:00 CEST	46	Slides are available from the FAIR IMPACT Zenodo Community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8282673 and the recording are available from the website https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-implementation-workshop-support-national-level-initiatives
	Monday 28 August 2023 15:00 – 16:00 CEST	72	Slides are available from the FAIR IMPACT Zenodo Community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8289096 and the recording are available from the website https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-implementation-workshop-support-research-performing-organisations
	Tuesday 29 August 2023 15:00 – 16:00 CEST	70	Slides are available from the FAIR IMPACT Zenodo Community https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8297850 and the recording are available from the website https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-impact-events/fair-implementation-workshop-support-repositories-data-service-providers

6 Next steps

Additional FAIR Implementation Workshops will be planned and delivered over the life of the project. A dedicated section of the website¹ has been created to list these events and to share the recordings and slides.

¹ FAIR Implementation Workshop series <https://fair-impact.eu/events/fair-implementation-workshops>

